
FRANCHISE SYSTEM IN BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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KEYWORDS

Franchising, franchisor, franchisee, advantages and disadvantages of the franchise system, franchise agreement

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on what franchising is, what it does, and how franchising is organized. The development of franchising in our country, its development, and efforts to organize it were shared. Information is provided about the role and use of franchising in life, as well as its benefits.

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BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKDA FRANCHAYZING TIZIMI

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

Franchayzing, franchayzer, franchayzi, Franchayzing tizimi afzallik tomoni va kamchilik taraflari, franchayzing shartnomasi

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada franchayzing nimaligini, u nimani bajarishi, franchayzing va qanday tashkil topishlari to‘g‘risida ma‘lumotlar berilgan. Franchayzingni mamlakatimizdagi taraqqiyoti, rivoj topishi va uni tashkil qilishdagi harakatlar baham ko‘rilgan. Franchayzing hayotda asosan qanday vazifani bajarishi va undan foydalanish, hamda uning foydali taraflari haqida ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Franchayzing - biznesni tashkil etish va rivojlantirish tizimi bo‘lib, unda bir kompaniya (franchayzer) boshqasiga yoki yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorga (franchayzi) nom va tizimdan foydalangan holda biznes yuritish huquqini beradi.

Franchayzing amalda faoliyat yuritayotgan xo‘jalik subyektining ishchanlik qobiliyati (imiji) va sinalgan barcha texnologiyalarini sotib olish yoki foydalanish huquqini anglatadi. Ushbu jarayonlar pul mablag‘lari to‘lovlari evaziga barcha texnologiyalar bilan birga tajriba va bilimlarni berish bilan amalga oshiriladi. Demak, franchayzer bir tomondan o‘z hamkorlariga faoliyat sohasining iste‘mol segmentini tanlash, savdo tarmog‘ini tashkil etish, samarali reklama qilish, malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda yordam bersa, ikkinchi tomondan esa boshqaruv va savdo muomalalarini tashkil etish bo‘yicha maslahat beradi.

Franchayzer o‘z savdo belgisidan foydalanganlik uchun pul ajratmasi oladi, ko‘pincha, xom ashyo va uning qismlar yetkazib berish va xodimlarni o‘qitishni ham ta‘minlaydi.

Franchayzi franchayzer tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan sxema bo‘yicha biznes yuritish huquqini sotib oladi (to‘lovlarni to‘laydi). Franchayzi o‘z savdo nuqtasini tayyorlash, ishga tushirish va ishlatish xarajatlarini o‘z zimmasiga oladi.

Har qanday franchayzing tizimining asosini tomonlarning vazifalarini o‘z ichiga oluvchi franchayzing shartnomasi tashkil qiladi.

O‘zbekistonda tovar belgisining bu "ijarasi" tobora kuchayib bormoqda. Franchezing rivojlanishga to‘sqinlik qiladigan asosiy omil - bu mamlakatimizdagi bu soha bo‘yicha yetarli bilim yetishmasligi. Buning bir qancha sabablari bor, lekin asosiysi ixtisoslashtirilgan ta‘limning etishmasligi. Franchayzing bilan har qanday tarzda shug‘ullanadigan biznes maktablari va ixtisoslashtirilgan kurslar juda kam.

Ikkinchi sabab - bu qurilish va biznes yuritishning nisbatan "yoshligi". Agar AQSh va Yevropada o‘tgan asrning 40-yillari oxiridan boshlab faol rivojlanayotgan bo‘lsa, MDH mamlakatlari iqtisodiyotida 2000-yillarning boshlaridan boshlangan.

Uchinchi sabab - qonunchilik bazasining nomukammalligi. Bu birinchi ikkita sabab bilan bog‘liq, chunki mansabdor shaxslar va deputatlar ham ushbu sabablar ta‘siriga tushib qolishadi.

O‘zbekistonda franchayzing muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanishi uchun, birinchi navbatda, ma‘rifiy ishlarni olib borish, tadbirkorlik sub‘ektlari va tadbirkorlarga tushuntirishlar

berish zarur. Mening fikrimcha YeTTBning qo'llab-quvvatlashi va yordami tufayli bu yo'nalishdagi ishlarni amalga oshirish mumkin deb o'ylayman. To'g'ri bu uzoq va mashaqqatli bo'lishi mumkin, lekin bu ish bajarilishi kerak.

Mening fikrimcha butun O'zbekiston aholisida franchayzing nima ekanligi haqida tushunchani shakllantirishimiz kerak. Axir, aslida, mamlakatimiz har qanday rezidenti franchayzing sotib olib, o'z biznesimizni boshlashimiz mumkin.

Franchayzing istisnosiz hamma uchun mavjud, ammo tadbirkorlar tushunishlari kerakki, biznes turiga qarab, franchayzing orqali ham butun model, ham jarayonlarning faqat bir qismi o'tkazilishi mumkin. Aynan shu yechim murakkab biznes modellarida samarali tarmoq yaratish imkonini beradi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, buni biznesga muqobil deb hisoblash mumkin emas, chunki bu uning ajralmas qismidir. Franchayzer uchun bu miqyoslash modeli, franchayzi uchun esa bu risklarni kamaytiradigan o'z biznesini yuritish shaklidir.

Franchayzing ma'lum bir "o'sish" bosqichidan o'tgan, ya'ni o'z modelini aniq bilgan, maqsadli auditoriyasini tekshirgan, o'z mahsuloti va uni takomillashtirish yo'llarini tushungan va ish tizimini yaratgan kompaniyalar tomonidan qo'llaniladi.

Dunyoning har qanday davlatida bo'lgani kabi bizning mamlakatimizda ham tadbirkorlar faoliyati ko'lami va ko'lamidan qat'i nazar, ushbu tizimdan foydalanish mumkin. Kompaniyaning o'lchamini kengaytirishga tayyorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omil kompaniyaning "to'ldirilganligi" dir. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, tizimlilik darajasi.

Mamlakatimizda o'ndan ortiq bunday kompaniyalar mavjud, bu ular o'z franchayzalarini yaratishi va franchayzilarni jalb qilish orqali tizimli biznes madaniyatini rivojlantirishi mumkin, bu esa o'z navbatida barqaror iqtisodiyot, yangi ish o'rinlari va mustahkamlanishga olib keladi.

O'zbekistonda franchayzingning eng keng tarqalgan turlari savdo va xizmat ko'rsatishdir. Iqtisodiyotga ta'sir darajasi bo'yicha bular mikro va kichik biznesdir. Qoida tariqasida, aynan shu ikki tur yangi iqtisodiy sharoitda faol rivojlana boshlaydi. Ular idrok qilish uchun biroz sodda, osonroq va tushunarli.

Franchayzingni rivojlantirishni rejalashtirayotgan kompaniyalar ko'proq talabni kutishlari mumkin. Aniqlik uchun men o'ziga xos turlarni sanab o'taman: oziq-ovqat va nooziq-ovqat chakana savdosi, restoranlar, kafelar, tez ovqatlanish, novvoyxonalar, go'zallik salonlari, ko'chmas mulk agentliklari, kimyoviy tozalashlar, maktablar, bolalar bog'chalari, fitnes markazlari, avtomobil yuvish va boshqalar.

Shuningdek, ishlab chiqarish va qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarini har doim talabga ega bo'lib kelgan, chunki ular allaqachon o'rta va yirik biznes toifasiga kiradi. Biroq, ularning yaratilishi muhim resurslarni talab qiladi va sotib olish arzon sarmoya bo'lmaydi. Lekin ular kelgusi yillar davomida ikkala tomonni ham yuqori rentabellik bilan ta'minlashi mumkin.

Farnchazingda foyda va xavflar haqida gapirsak mening fikrimcha franchayzingni tizimlashtirish, takomillashtirish va rivojlantirishning haqiqiy vositasi deb o'ylayman. To'g'ri ishlab chiqilgan franchayzing bilan ikkala tomon ham hamkorlikdan yakka o'zi

biznes yuritgandan ko'ra bir necha baravar ko'proq foyda ko'radi.

Shunday qilib, birinchi tomon sezilarli investitsiyalarsiz bozor ulushini tezroq egallashi, daromadlarni oshirishi, shuningdek, chekka hududlarga tarqalishi mumkin.

Xaridorlar yangi joy tanlash, resurslarni tejash, tajribali hamkor tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash, innovatsiyalar va yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanish, xavflarni diversifikatsiya qilish va boshqa ko'p imkoniyatlarga ega bo'ladilar.

Bu erda siz muhimligi, afzalliklari va afzalliklariga qaramay, quyidagi xavflar mavjudligini tushunishingiz kerak:

- mahsulotning bozor manfaatlariga mos kelmasligi;
- hududning samarasiz rivojlanishi;
- murakkab tarmoqlarni boshqarish tajribasining etishmasligi;
- past sifatli franchayzing tufayli obro'ning yo'qolishi;
- franchayzilarning yo'qolishi tufayli raqobatdosh ustunliklarni yo'qotish;
- brending aralashmasi.

Endi O'zbekistondagi franchayzing brendlari haqida gapirsak. Bularni quyidagi diagramma orqali ko'rish mumkin:

Bu diagramma orqali O'zbekistondagi bir qancha franchayzingning bir qancha turlari va uning qancha darajada rivojlanganligi haqida ma'lumot berishga harakat qildik.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki, franchayzing bu biror turdagi biznesni boshqa joylarda ham rivojlantirish va uning brendini yanada tanitish kabi vazifalarni bajaradi. Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, bir turdagi biror bir tovarni boshqa joydagi shaxslar ham ishlatish imkoniyatini yaratadi hamda shu shaklda ish olib boruvchi biznes turlari ko'proq foyda olishini ko'rsatadi. Ya'ni, bu kam tавvagalchilik orqali ko'proq foyda degani. Franchayzingni har bir davlatda amalga oshirish mumkin. Hozirda mamlakatimizda bu faoliyat turi bo'yicha shug'ullanuvchilar mavjud. Bu soha bo'yicha shug'ullanuvchilar brenddagi mahsulotlardan foydalanishadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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